

FELINE RHINOTRACHEITIS IN THE POPULATION DISEASE SPREAD.

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ABSTRACT

The main reason for this disease is that vaccination is a rare procedure for cats in our country. This disease affects the respiratory system. Kittens and adult cats are at the highest risk.

Severity of disease: Primary infection is usually the most severe. After recovery, the cat remains a carrier, but in stressful situations (relocation, new animals, pregnancy, infection with other infections, etc.), rhinotracheitis can appear again. Corticosteroid administration can also cause the virus to reactivate in an infected cat. Feline herpes virus is ubiquitous and vaccination against it is mandatory for all cats. Herpesvirus is the most common cause of upper respiratory infections in adult cats and kittens. Cats in stressful situations and where multiple cats live together, such as catteries and shelters, are at significantly higher risk.

Literature analysis: The virus is quite stable in the external environment. It is sensitive to strongly acidic and weakly alkaline pH values, inactivates in 3-4 minutes at 56°C, in 36 hours at 37°C, slow inactivation in formalin, resistant to ethyl alcohol. Destroy the virus shell with

standard disinfectants (hypochlorite, quaternary ammonium compounds).

Pathogenesis: In the usual course of infection, the multiplication of the virus in the epithelium of the nasopharynx, the nasal cavity, the tonsils, the epithelium of the upper trachea, the maxillary lymph nodes and the cornea can also be affected. Epithelial cells itch and form necrosis foci. The virus is adsorbed on leukocytes and causes viremia. When passing through the transplacental barrier, the brain, placenta and uterus are damaged. The tropism of the virus to the growing parts of the skeleton of kittens was determined experimentally.

Diagnosis of rhinotracheitis in cats: the cat is examined at the Constellation Veterinary Clinic (SVAO). There are other diseases with similar symptoms, so differential diagnosis is carried out. Nasal or eye discharge is analyzed by PCR in a veterinary laboratory. This method allows

you to clearly understand whether the cat is infected with the herpes virus. In addition to this test, a biochemical and

general analysis of the cat's blood and urine analysis may be necessary.

Measures to prevent rhinotracheitis in cats. The mechanism of action consists in suppressing the reproduction of DNA and RNA viruses in infected cells, increasing the resistance of healthy cells of the body to virus infection, increasing the phagocytic activity of macrophages, and increasing the specific cytotoxicity of lymphocytes. Clinical signs: The incubation period lasts from 2 to 10 days. The acute course is characterized by serous conjunctivitis, rhinitis, sneezing, increased salivation,

anorexia, fever (39.5-40°C). The mucous membranes of the nose, pharynx, larynx are sharply swollen, swollen, often hyperemic ("red nose"). Affected cats develop shortness of breath. White plaques, necrotic crusts appear on the surface of the nose and mucous membrane, and ulcers form under them. When palpating the larynx and trachea, cats have severe pain and anxiety. Difficulty eating and drinking.

Recommendations: Make sure the cat is eating and drinking. Support in the form of more attractive foods, flavor enhancers, or tube feeding may be needed if the cat is not eating regular food. In severe cases, intravenous or subcutaneous infusion is

used. Humidifiers are used to make breathing easier. If this is not the case, you can put the cat in the bathroom with the shower turned on for 10-15 minutes (do not allow overheating while doing this !!!)

References:

1. Modern Veterinary Medicine, Issue 5, 2015.
2. Internet data